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Models for Combustion Chamber, Propeller Noise and Electric Power System

Project: 101096055

INtegration and Digital demonstration of low- emission aircraft technoloGies and airport Operations

INDIGO

**Work package: WP2 - Performance and Noise Model of Distributed
Hybrid Electric Propulsion**

Deliverable: D2.1

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1 Tasks description and starting conditions

The deliverable 2.1 encompasses the development of models of combustion chamber, propeller noise and electric power system, which represent sub-models for an overall model of a hybrid-electric propulsion model of turbo-prop engine.

Combustion Chamber Model:

The reduced-order combustion chamber model for a gas turbine of an turbo-prop engine operating with SAF, created by the project partner from Ruhr University Bochum, accounts for pollutant emissions. For a preliminary evaluation of this model, two different combustion modelling approaches were employed: a 0D-Chemical Equilibrium (CE) and a Chemical Reactor Network (CRN), described in detail in Sec. 2.2. The results are compared with manufacturers' data provided by [ICAO2023] for a reference engine (CFM56-7B27) in Sec. 2.3.

The results confirm the validity of the reduced-order combustion chamber model based on the CRN approach. Despite the simplicity of the CRN model and the high uncertainty in measuring real engine reference data, predictions of the main pollutant species concentrations align with engine manufacturers' data.

Additionally, lookup tables were created based on the CRN model results for SAF (see Sec. 2.4). These tables enable the integration of the combustion chamber model into the gas turbine model of the hybrid-electric propulsion system, which is being developed by project partner TUBS (Deliverable 2.2). The use of lookup tables allows flexible model integration and efficient calculation of pollutant emissions of the hybrid-electric propulsion model.

Propeller Noise Model:

Propeller Noise Models representing a low, medium, and high-fidelity level characterization of the propeller sound generation mechanism have been prepared by research partners UoB and DLR to support the power train design with dedicated noise assessments for a larger set of variations. As an essential prerequisite, this requires an automated evaluation of a considerable set of alternative power train settings

In advance, all involved partners agreed to share power train data by means of dedicated csv-data tables, which enables an evaluation of O(100) different propulsor settings. This document documents also formally promotes the proper setup up of interfaces and workflows that enables the processing of the envisaged amount of data from the power train design partners.

Hybrid Electric Propulsion Model:

The electrical network design of the Hybrid Electric Propulsion power train was developed using the EPS development methodology [Jones2021]. To model

and evaluate the design, the methodology also incorporates the Strathclyde Systems Tool for preliminary sizing, power flow modelling and contingency operation evaluation. Additionally, transient modelling is also included for more dynamic electrical performance verification.

The main inputs of the Strathclyde Systems Tool (SST) incorporate technology datasets of the various electrical power components such as power density and efficiency from public roadmaps and incorporates these into the system level power flow and sizing evaluation against EPU power demands aligned with the pre-set mission profile. The power flow and sizing evaluation additionally considers discrete electrical and engine failure cases to consider oversizing requirements of the system to ensure adequate power flow under failure scenarios. Transient models of the electrical power system have been developed to verify the operation of the proposed electrical power system during failure modes. These transient models do not interact directly with the wider propulsive power train.

A wider parameter sweep using the models examines different variation of hybridisation levels (shaft power of EPUs derived from thrust provision split between the EPUs and engine driven turboprops) and electrical source split (power split for electrical source to EPUs from generators and batteries). The sweeps allow the generation of lookup tables of sizing and power flow outputs. These lookup tables are to be further integrated with the wider models of the consortium to capture the interface design of the power train including engine and propeller design.

2 Combustion Chamber Model and SAF

A combustion chamber for a gas turbine of the hybrid-electric propulsion system has been modelled using two different approaches. The first approach involves a 0D-chemical equilibrium (CE) method, utilizing the EBSILON®Professional 16.1.0.33123 tool. The second approach employs a simplified 0D-chemical reaction network (CRN), generated with the open-source software Cantera 3.0.0 [Goodwin2023] and following a similar strategy as described in [Villette2023]. Both modelling approaches represent an idealized version of the combustion chamber by dividing the flame tube into three control volumes, corresponding to primary, secondary, and dilution zones typical of a Rich-Burn, Quick-Mix, Lean-Burn (RQL)-type combustor. The combustion physics within these volumes are calculated using the mentioned approaches.

2.1 Background on Chemical Reactor Networks

The Chemical Reactor Network (CRN) methodology [Slavinskaya2023, Åkerblom2023] is a widely utilized technique for reduced-order modelling of combustion processes. This approach simplifies a complex system into interconnected reactors, each representing a specific zone within the overall system. In chemical engineering, a reactor refers to any system where reactants undergo conversion to products through one or more chemical reactions. For an aircraft gas turbine engine, the combustion chamber can be subdivided into multiple zones based on distinct mixing characteristics. Each zone constitutes volume or “node” of the reaction network and is virtually represented by a reactor. Consequently, the focus shifts towards macroscopic mixing patterns.

Three primary reactor types used in CRN are:

1. Perfectly Stirred Reactor (PSR), 0-Dimensional: reactants are assumed to be perfectly mixed, resulting in a uniform composition and temperature throughout.
2. Partially Stirred Reactor (PaSR), 0-Dimensional: the flow is considered zero-dimensional, but partial mixing of species is taken into account, representing a more realistic scenario in turbulent combustion zones, particularly in the primary zone where significant fluctuations in mixing quality occur.
3. Plug Flow Reactor (PFR), 1-Dimensional: reactants flow through a cylindrical tube, and reactions occur along the flow path. This model assumes that concentration and temperature vary along the reactor length.

One of CRN's main advantages is the ability to incorporate detailed kinetic mechanisms within each reactor zone, providing insights into species formation pathways even in complex systems.

The design process for a CRN can be summarized as follows:

1. Identification of mixing zones: analyse the flow field in the combustion device (measured or predicted) to identify regions with similar temperature, velocity, and species concentration profiles that can constitute a node of the network.
2. Arrangement of reactors: determine the number of reactors based on the identified zones and choose the appropriate reactor type for each zone, considering predominant physical/chemical processes.
3. Integration of an appropriate kinetic mechanism: incorporate detailed or reduced kinetic mechanisms into each reactor zone to accurately model chemical reactions and predict species formation pathways.

2.2 CRN and CE Model for Pollutant Emission Evaluation

The combustion chamber model follows the concept known as Rich-Burn, Quick-Mix, Lean-Burn (RQL), which is commonly used in modern aircraft gas turbines to minimize the emission of NO_x , CO, and UHC. To consider this concept, the flame tube geometry of the combustion chamber is divided into three distinct zones: primary zone (PZ), secondary zone (SZ), and dilution zone (DZ), as shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Schematic cross-section view of a combustion chamber (adapted from [Jackowski2021]).

In the primary zone, a rich air-fuel mixture is combusted using only an initial fraction of the total airflow coming from the upstream compressor to ensure stable combustion. This mixture then transitions to the secondary zone where it is further mixed with additional air and cooled, or "quenched," to reduce NO_x production rates. Finally, in the dilution zone, the remaining airflow is added to create a lean mixture that allows for the oxidation of partially burned hydrocarbons.

Figure 2: Abstracted reduced-order combustor model.

These zones are modelled using reactor components connected by mass flows with corresponding gas properties and compositions (**Figure 2**). Gibbs reactors are employed for the CE approach, while perfectly stirred reactors are used for the CRN approach. Reservoirs are also included to represent infinite volumes, ensuring a constant supply of air and fuel with consistent gas properties and compositions. The airflow is distributed among the reactors according to the factors A_i ($i = \{PZ, SZ, DZ\}$), as listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Operating points and data for combustion chamber models.

	Operating Scenarios			
	Take-off	Climb	Approach	Idle
Power Setting [%]	100	85	30	7
$T_{t,in}$ [K]	795	759	619	477
\dot{m}_{air} [kg/s]	47.47	42.8	21.33	8.32
FAR [1]	0.026	0.024	0.016	0.014
A_{PZ} [%]			0.3082	
A_{SZ} [%]			0.2302	
A_{DZ} [%]			0.4616	
V_{PZ} [m ³]			0.007037	
V_{SZ} [m ³]			0.006882	
V_{DZ} [m ³]			0.020801	
$\Delta p\%$ [%]			5.01	

In case of the CE model, reservoirs are not utilized; instead, inlet conditions for air and fuel mass flows are specified directly at the reactor inlets, and the exhaust gas is released into the environment after passing through a valve component that accounts for combustion chamber pressure loss.

In case of the CRN model, ignition of the combustion process must be initiated by setting the initial temperature of 1900 K in the first reactor (PZ) to a

sufficiently high value, thereby igniting the air-fuel mixture in the downstream zones/reactors. Combustion reactions in subsequent reactors (SZ and DZ) are then triggered by the combustion products from the PZ reactor.

2.3 CRN Model Validation

In order to assess the accuracy of combustion chamber models created, calculated emission products from four operating scenarios (take-off, climb, approach, idle) were compared to data from the ICAO databank [ICAO2023]. The ICAO databank contains standardized exhaust emissions information for certified turbofan and turbojet engines of production aircraft. For validation purposes, data from the CFM56-7B27 engine, a two-spool high-bypass turbofan engine, were used. Required geometry data and operating conditions were prepared based on [Villette2023] and are summarized in Table 1.

The combustion chamber inlet conditions are defined by pressure $p_{t,in}$, temperature $T_{t,in}$, and air mass flow rate \dot{m}_{air} . The fuel mass flow rate is determined by the fuel-to-air ratio (FAR) or air-to-fuel ratio (AFR), respectively. The air mass flow rate distribution to each combustion chamber zone (A_i) remains constant for all operating scenarios considered.

In case of the CRN model, volumes of each combustion chamber zone V_i affect the residence time of combustion gases and consequently exhaust gas emission products. For kinetic reaction mechanisms, the model of [Luche2003] was applied, with jet fuel defined by surrogate composition according to [Wang2012].

Figure 3 presents the results as emission indices EI for nitrogen oxides (NO_x = NO + NO₂), carbon monoxide (CO) and unburned hydrocarbons (UHC) for four operating scenarios of the engine. Power setting values characterize the operating scenarios: 100 % (take-off), 85 % (climb), 30 % (approach), and 7 % (idle).

The CE model does not accurately predict UHC and CO emissions, but it can reproduce NO_x emission trends with deviations by a factor of about 2.5 during take-off and climb scenarios due to the assumption of infinite residence time in the primary zone.

In contrast, the CRN model shows satisfactory agreement with ICAO validation data for both NO_x and CO emissions, while underpredicting UHC emissions, although it qualitatively reproduces increasing UHC emissions for operating scenarios with lower power demands (approach and idle). The discrepancy observed in the UHC predictions will be the subject of further investigation using more complex reduced order models (including PaSR and PFR) whilst assessing the differences in surrogate fuels and fuel conversion rates of available mechanisms (see for example fuel A2 skeletal [Wang2018]).

Compared to [Villette2023], who also used a CRN model with three reactors, the present approach shows satisfactory agreement. Overall, the CRN model provides a solid basis for realistically determining combustion chamber emissions and subsequent work steps.

Figure 3: Results of reduced-order combustion chamber models compared to ICAO data.

2.4 Integration into Hybrid-Electric Propulsion System Model

The combustion chamber models developed are integrated into the gas turbine of the hybrid-electric propulsion system using lookup tables. This approach allows for an efficient and versatile incorporation of combustion models of any complexity. The lookup table contains only intensive variables, ensuring that the combustion chamber model is independent of the gas turbine size.

The input variables for the lookup table include the Air-to-Fuel Ratio (AFR) or Fuel-to-Air Ratio (FAR) and the combustion chamber inlet temperature $T_{t,3}$. As the combustion process is assumed to be isobaric, pressure is not considered as an input variable.

The outlet temperature $T_{t,4}$ of the combustion chamber is determined by solving the energy equation for the combustion chamber model. The results are then integrated into the lookup table, enabling a fast bi-linear interpolation to determine the combustion chamber outlet temperature $T_{t,4}$ without having to solve the energy equation in the hybrid-electric propulsion system model.

Additionally, the mass concentrations of all combustion products are included in the lookup table, allowing for the determination of the emission profile at the combustion chamber outlet.

A second lookup table is constructed similarly and used to describe the state properties of the exhaust gas ($FAR > 0$) and air ($FAR = 0$) according to [McBride1996] at any position within the gas turbine of the hybrid-electric propulsion system.

To consider the chemical kinetics of SAF, a literature study on reaction mechanisms and surrogates of SAF was conducted and in a first step the model of [Park2019] for an alcohol-to-jet fuel was employed.

Finally, the lookup tables are prepared with a subsequent MATLAB script to integrate the combustion chamber model into the MATLAB-based gas turbine model on a plug-and-play basis. This step has already been done successfully.

3 Propeller Noise Model

Propeller Noise Models representing a low, medium, and high-fidelity level characterization of the propeller sound generation mechanism have been prepared by research partners UoB and DLR to support the power train design with dedicated noise assessments for a larger set of variations. As an essential prerequisite, this requires an automated evaluation of a considerable set of alternative power train settings

In advance, all involved partners agreed to share power train data by means of dedicated csv-data tables, which enables an evaluation of O(100) different propulsor settings. This document documents also formally promotes the proper setup up of interfaces and workflows that enables the processing of the envisaged amount of data from the power train design partners.

To proceed along this lines, 6 specific propeller settings were provided by TUBS to DLR and UoB, which comprise 3 inboard and 3 outboard propeller settings, as documented in Table 1. The considered cases serve only as proof of operation of the workflow and refer to cruise conditions at 8000 m cruise altitude, not to take off cases which would be of higher relevance for the immediate noise pollution at the ground.

Table 1: Definition of 3 out- and 3 inboard propeller cases based on cruise speed and cruise altitude 8000m.

Prop Case	No. Blades	R [m]	Thrust [N]	Power [kW]	RPM [1/min]	Flight Speed [m/s]	rho [kg/m ³]	cT [-]
OB #1	3	2,00	2454,48	497,05	661,90	184,84	0,524878	0,15
OB #2	3	2,00	3272,64	670,81	661,90	184,84	0,524878	0,20
OB #3	3	2,00	4090,81	849,61	661,90	184,84	0,524878	0,25
IB #1	5	2,50	7670,34	1.616,15	529,52	184,84	0,524878	0,30
IB #2	5	2,50	8948,65	1.913,99	529,52	184,84	0,524878	0,35
IB #3	5	2,50	10226,73	2.223,21	529,52	184,84	0,524878	0,40

The individual propeller settings correspond to a design configuration with one inboard propeller and four electrically driven outboard propeller, refer to Figure 1.

Figure 4: INDIGO A/C with geometry from CPACS definition and propeller setting with 1 inboard and 4 outboard propellers.

The inboard propeller is assumed to operate at one of the specified inboard conditions as defined in the table above (cases indicated by “IB”, larger propeller diameter in the figure). The four outboard propellers are assumed to operate all at equal settings as specified by one of the above outboard definitions (cases indicated by “OB”, smaller propeller diameter in the figure), i.e. at this stage no differential thrust settings are accounted for, but in general can be treated by the workflow.

Therefore, the combination of all inboard and outboard settings result in 9 different thrust settings.

For the simulation of propeller noise based UoB and DLR have applied the following type of models, sorted from low- to high fidelity levels:

Isolated Propeller Noise Models

- a. Modified & extended Gutin-type propeller model proposed by Delfs that has been used in WP1 also for preliminary design to compute EPN levels for approach, take-off, cut-back, and sideline; the model does not account for the actual radial blade load distribution but is based on an improved representation of blade loads at a specific radial position (DLR)
- b. Tonal noise prediction is produced using a frequency domain method originally developed by Hanson, in which the blade thickness and loading components are derived from chordwise thickness and lift distribution. The model developed by UoB implemented a simplification of constant lift distribution and parabolic thickness distribution in the chordwise direction, which is widely used in other aerospace vehicle design tools.

The broadband noise prediction was conducted using an analytical and empirical approach to estimate trailing edge noise. This method relies on Amiet's frequency domain formulation, which computes the trailing edge noise spectrum based on pressure fluctuations near the trailing edge. The contributions from each blade section are summed and integrated over the azimuthal coordinate of the blade to account for Doppler effects. This enables an efficient estimation of broadband noise without requiring high-resolution simulations, making it suitable for practical applications

- c. Ffowcs-Williams and Hawkings (FW-H) based description of propeller noise with flight effects with the DLR solver APSIM utilizing radial blade load descriptions as provided by TUBS from blade element momentum theory (BEMT) together with the specification of geometrical feature of the propeller to account for the thickness effects (DLR)

Installed Propeller Noise Model

- d. Volume resolving CAA on hierarchical-cartesian (octree-cartesian) grids with immersed boundary method (PIANO-IBM) to simulate installed propeller noise for one reference case to evaluate the importance of installation effects that are not captured by the lower fidelity isolated propeller models (DLR)

At this stage of refined powertrain design, it is formally foreseen according to DoW to use simplified propeller tools only that account for the noise generated by the isolated propeller and considers the entire power train by the energetic summation of all propulsors involved.

However, it is assumed that further noise effects will arise due to the interaction of the rotors with each other and effects of the propellers from the installation at the wing. Installation effects e.g. come from the interaction of the propeller blade tip and hub vortices with the leading edge of the wing, which results in the generation of leading-edge noise at the wing. Furthermore, the close proximity of the wing leading edge to the propeller plane will alter the incident flow angles at the propeller blade, thus causing some blade load modulations that could give rise to extra noise. Furthermore, the hydrodynamic near field

pressure field of the propeller can become scattered at the wing leading edge, thus causing installation contributions. Finally, broadband noise is caused by the installation in various ways. For example, the turbulent propeller wake could interact with the wing leading edge and the propeller slip stream will increase velocities at the wing trailing edge thus generating higher levels of wing trailing edge noise.

To capture the rich physics involved in the acoustic sound generation process of the installed propeller, higher-fidelity simulation tools are required that inevitably require a significant increase in the amount of computational resources involved. The cross-comparison and development of installed propeller models is the subject of INDIGO WP3.3. However, DLR agreed to make already in the framework of WP2.3 one simulation under installation conditions to make a first assessment of the additional penalty stemming from installed propeller effects on the overall sound.

Sample results from the workflow of the different models are shown below.

a. extended Gutin-type model (Delfs model)

Figure 5: Resulting sound pressure levels of all six propeller settings under cruise conditions; first five harmonics shown for each propeller setting.

Results from the Delfs model are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6. In the first figure predicted peak levels are depicted for the first 5 propeller harmonics for all specified test cases. The qualitative trend corresponds with the prediction of UoB. Peak levels above 80dB for the first harmonic are slightly higher.

Furthermore, a steeper drop-off, albeit less steep as in the original Gutin model, can be observed. The steeper drop-off of higher harmonics presumably results from the fact that the model is mainly tuned for the flight phase during take off and approach and is less suitable under cruise conditions.

Directivities for all cases for OASPL and all considered harmonics are depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Directivity of all 6 propeller settings from Gutin-type model.

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b. Hanson model

Figure 7 to Figure 10 show the results from Hanson model for all 6 propeller designs calculated for cruise conditions at 8000m (26247ft).

The results using low-fidelity aeroacoustic simulations for the different propeller designs reveal some insights into the behaviour of tonal and broadband noise characteristics.

Figure 7 shows that all propellers exhibited reasonable levels of the first BPF Sound Pressure Level, showcasing similar trends for different designs. The predicted amplitude at the blade passing frequency agrees reasonably well with that of the Gutin-based model, shown in Figure 5. However, the observed high decay rate in the tonal harmonics suggests that some limitation exists for the present prediction model. The model's simplifications might overlook factors such as compressibility effects as well as the spanwise blade behaviour, potentially leading to an underprediction of the harmonics

Figure 7: Sound pressure levels of the first five harmonics calculated from Hanson Model of all six propeller settings under cruise conditions.

The analysis of directivity for tonal and broadband noise components presented in Figure 8 and Figure 9 indicates a noteworthy inverse relationship between tonal noise and broadband SPL. Propellers that generated higher tonal noise levels tended to present lower broadband noise (outboard propellers), and conversely, those with elevated broadband SPL exhibited reduced tonal levels (inboard propellers). This suggests that the design features promoting tonal noise — potentially related to blade shape or angle of attack — may lead to mitigations of the broadband noise. Yet, it is useful to note that the low-fidelity

nature of the present broadband prediction should be interpreted with care, and yet, it is noteworthy for further investigations in the prospective work packages.

Figure 8: Sound pressure levels directivities of the first five harmonics for each propeller design under cruise conditions.

Figure 9: Sound pressure levels directivities of the broadband noise for each propeller design under cruise conditions.

The OASPL directivities presented in Figure 10 reveal intriguing patterns, including the maximum values associated with different propeller designs. Inboard propellers, which exhibits lower first BPF values and higher

Figure 10: Overall sound pressure levels directivities for each propeller design under cruise conditions.

broadband levels demonstrate slightly lower maximum OASPL values. The distinct shapes of the directivity patterns further emphasize this relationship.

- Propellers with lower maximum OASPL (inboard propellers) exhibit shapes characterized by a broader, more circular directivity pattern. This pattern indicates a more omnidirectional radiation characteristic, likely

influenced by higher levels of broadband noise that radiate across a wider area.

- In contrast, propellers with higher maximum OASPL show a more focused emission pattern resembling a dipole. The presence of this dipole-like pattern suggests that tonal noise characteristics dominate, leading to higher sound levels in targeted areas (for instance, towards the pedestrian) while maintaining lower levels elsewhere.

These differences in directivity shapes highlight how various design features impact the overall acoustic signature of the propellers.

In summary, while the BEMT-Hanson model provides a useful framework for initial analyses, its low fidelity may contribute to some inaccuracies in predicting SPL decay rates and noise characteristics, encouraging the use of higher-fidelity models approaches to better capture the intricacies of propeller aerodynamics and acoustics.

c. FW-H Method (DLR APSIM Code)

Simulation results for the APSIM code are discussed next. As the code works with rotating blades in the time domain, it is relatively straight forward to consider OASPL metrics. Sound radiation on a sphere and extracted directivities are shown in the subsequent figures.

The effect of flight velocity is accounted for and clearly visible in polar plots. The entire set was simulated assuming sea level conditions. The cruise altitude correction was computed for case IB03, shown in Figure 13. In general, the OASPL peak noise levels are in line with the other prediction tools. Relative trends are captured, and noise directivities are consistent for the given input data, thus, highlighting the capability of the present methods to properly account for design delta effects.

Figure 11: FW-H computations of the inboard propeller.

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OB015

OB015

OB02

OB02

OB025

OB025

Figure 12: FW-H simulations of the outboard propeller settings.

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Figure 13: IB03 at cruise conditions.

d. Installed propeller noise (PIANO-IBM)

Installed propeller noise simulation for the INDIGO aircraft at full scale are discussed next. The simulations have been carried out on an octree cartesian grid accounting for the exact representation of the aircraft. The method makes use of the low dispersive and dissipative DRP scheme of Tam & Webb and involves hanging nodes to enable multi domain treatment on octree cartesian grids. Three refinement levels are considered for the present case.

The grid consists of 146Mio grid points. Further details are listed below. As part of the simulation the propeller wake is resolved and its interaction with the airframe time accurately resolved.

Figure 14: PIANO-IBM Simulation Grid of the Aircraft at Full Scale.

CASE	INDIGO INSTALLED
No blocks	10743
No points	146E6
dims per block	31 pts x 21 pts x 21 pts
Dims domain	50 m x 60 m x 20 m
Acoustic resolution	340 Hz
Dt*	5.E-3
Dt	1.47E-5s
Performance	$35 \frac{\mu s}{pt\ steps}$
No CPUs	1343

Figure 15: Simulation details; the grid consists of 10.743 blocks; simulations are running on 1343 CPUs; all first 5 higher harmonics are directly resolved.

Figure 16: Snapshot of the simulation clearly revealing the propeller wake and wing interaction.

4 Electric Power System Model

The baseline INDIGO aircraft has two turbo-props, each driven by a gas turbine engine and 8 electrically driven propellers (e-propellers), with 4 e-propellers in each wing. The EPS design methodology presented in [Jones2021] was applied to develop the baseline EPS design in **Figure 4**. This is described in detail in [Fong 2024].

Figure 4: Indigo candidate EPS design.

The baseline EPS design, splits the EPS into 4 separate channels which are operated in isolation under normal conditions in flight to limit propagation of electrical faults. This 4-channel approach to enable fault isolation is similar to the approach taken by both more-electric aircraft, such as the Boeing 787 [Xu2017], and the concept hybrid-electric IMOTHEP “Short-Medium Range Conservative” aircraft [Schmollgruber 2019] [IMOTHEP 2021]. For the INDIGO aircraft, each channel has a battery and generator and powers two EPU’s. Bus ties are also included to allow for inter-channel power transfer during failure scenarios.

The EPS can operate either in a serial-hybrid configuration [NASA2024], with the gas turbine driven generators in Figure 4 running as generators, or in a parallel/serial-hybrid configuration [DeVries 2018] with the electrical machines on the gas turbines run as motors. In this parallel-series set up, electrical power is provided solely by the batteries.

4.1 Interface of Electrical Model with Full Propulsion Power Train

Once a baseline EPS was established, a methodology was needed to provide appropriate datasets to interface the EPS with the wider propulsion power train. The electrical model interfaces with the wider INDIGO power train as indicated in Figure 5 (the EPS model illustrated as the green block within this). The EPS model takes in the EPU power profile over the mission and outputs EPS weight, efficiency and generator off-take power demand.

Figure 5: EPS model (green block) in relation to wider power train modelling.

4.2 Strathclyde Systems Tool (SST)

4.2.1 SST Overview

The Strathclyde Systems Tool (SST), is a Python based tool that allows preliminary electrical network design evaluation. The SST enables examination of electrical component sizing and power flow for the EPU power demand aligned for a pre-set aircraft mission profile. The SST fits within “Level 1” of the EPS Modelling Framework [Jones 2021], which aligns to Architectural Level modelling defined in SAE AIR 6326 [SAE2015].

Figure 6 outlines the structure of the SST. The tool takes in a pre-defined EPS architecture. The input mission profile, hybridisation factor and power split between electrical power sources are processed within the tool to provide data on electrical load requirements and power flows. Within the context of the INDIGO project, the tool returns estimated weight and efficiencies for an EPS architecture.

Within INDIGO, the SST served two purposes. First, the SST enabled system design trades to be carried out for the EPS design [Fong2024]. Second, the SST was utilised to provide the required datasets to interface with the gas turbine model.

Figure 6: Overview of the SST structure, inputs and outputs.

4.2.2 SST Inputs

The inputs to the SST are based around low fidelity approximate representation of the different EPS equipment and sub-systems at steady state.

The inputs to the tool are summarised as follows:

- EPS architecture as a network of component nodes and connection edges
- EPU power demand aligned against overall mission profile (altitude, Mach number, thrust)
- Hybridization factor
- Electrical power split between different electrical sources (battery, generator)
- x, y, z coordinates for physical location of components in airframe.
- Performance datasets for electrical components.
 - These datasets include power density, efficiency, energy density, cost, volume and failure rates for electrical power system components.
 - The component database captures these technology attributes with different database versions possible for representing projection timelines and roadmaps.

- Datasets used for the INDIGO project have been populated with data from the published literature. Sources are referenced in Table 1.
- To align with the focus of the INDIGO project, for INDIGO datasets included power or energy (for energy storage) density, efficiency and failure rates.

The focus of the study for INDIGO is to establish the design of the EPS specific to the propulsion drive train. Hence neither the weight of the electric engine start equipment nor the EPS for non-propulsive systems, both of which are shown in the baseline architecture in Figure 4, is considered at this stage.

Table 1: Datasets used in the Strathclyde Systems Tool for the case study.

EPS Component	Failure rate (failure rate/flight hour)	Power, energy or current density.	Efficiency (%)	Projected year
Motor	9.24×10^{-6} [23]	13 kW/kg [24]	96 [16]	2026
AC-DC converter	power 2.7×10^{-5} [23]	22 kW/kg [24]	99 [16]	2026
DC-DC converter	power 2.7×10^{-5} [23]	15 kW/kg [24]	99 [16]	2026
Generator	1.3×10^{-4} [23]	21.3 kW/kg [25]	98.5 [25]	2035
Battery	9.31×10^{-5} [23]	400 WH/kg (pack level) [26]	98 [29]	2035
Solid State Breaker	Circuit 1.7×10^{-7} [21]	200 kW/kg [16]	99.5 [16]	2035
Cable	2×10^{-5}	170 A/(kg/m) [26]	99.9 [16]	2035
Busbar	1×10^{-6} [28]	Calculate based on copper density	99	-

An example mission-based power profile input to the SST is shown as Figure 7. Both normal operating and failure conditions are represented. Specifically, for the sizing aspect, the algorithm within the SST selects peak power demand requirements throughout all corner cases to derive a complete network solution which can satisfy all cases. This ensures that the EPS is sized to accommodate peak power demand.

Figure 7: Example baseline mission profile for concept aircraft (approximate total aircraft shaft power).

To capture the normal and failure cases, these scenarios are pre-set in an input file and loaded directly into the tool. An example of the input file is shown as Figure 8

Figure 8: input file to define normal and failure cases.

Table 2,

Parameter	Description	Unit
ρ_{power}	Electrical Component power density. Constant value for each component From literature	kW/kg
ρ_{energy}	Electrical component energy density. Constant value for each component From literature	WH/kg

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λ	Electrical component failure rate. Constant value for each component From Literature	Failures per Flight Hour
η	Electrical component efficiency. Constant value From Literature	%
X_{EPU}	EPU quantity (2x4,.....2x1)	QTY
Power(t)	EPU shaft power requirements in kW over mission profile	kW, s
Altitude(t)	EPU shaft power requirements in kW over mission profile	m, s
H-factor	Hybridisation factor for power split between turboshaft and EPU	%
ES-split	Electrical source split supplying EPU from generators and battery (below 900m)	%

and Table 4 provide detail of the input and output variables to/from the tool including definition of each parameter specific to the INDIGO design studies.

Table 2: SST input variables and definitions.

Parameter	Description	Unit
ρ_{power}	Electrical Component power density. Constant value for each component From literature	kW/kg
ρ_{energy}	Electrical component energy density. Constant value for each component From literature	WH/kg
λ	Electrical component failure rate. Constant value for each component From Literature	Failures per Flight Hour
η	Electrical component efficiency. Constant value From Literature	%
X_{EPU}	EPU quantity (2x4,.....2x1)	QTY
Power(t)	EPU shaft power requirements in kW over mission profile	kW, s
Altitude(t)	EPU shaft power requirements in kW over mission profile	m, s
H-factor	Hybridisation factor for power split between turboshaft and EPUs	%
ES-split	Electrical source split supplying EPU from generators and battery (below 900m)	%

Table 3: SST output variables and definitions.

Parameter	Description	Unit
m_{system}	System weight	kg
	System weight breakdown	kg
$\lambda_{\text{subsystem}}$	System failure rate	Failures per Flight Hour
η_{system}	System efficiency	%
$P_{\text{in system}}$	System power demand required by generator	kW

Table 4: H-factor and electrical source (ES) split equations.

Parameter Name	Equation	Unit	Terms	Description
H-factor	$\frac{P_{EPUs}}{P_{Turboshaft} + P_{EPUs}} 100\%$	%	P_{EPUs} is the propulsive shaft power from the e-propellers, and $P_{Turboshaft}$ is shaft power from the turbo-prop	Hybridisation factor for power split between turboshaft and EPUs
ES split	$\frac{P_{Generator}}{P_{Generator} + P_{Battery}} 100\%$	%	$P_{Generator}$ is the total power from the generators going into the e-propellers, and $P_{Battery}$ is the total power from the Batteries going into the e-propellers	Electrical source split supplying EPU from generators and battery (below 900m)

4.3 SST Operation when applied to the INDIGO Aircraft

4.3.1 Overview of SST Processes

The flow chart in Figure 9 outlines the process within the SST to sweep through different levels of hybridisation (H) and split between different energy sources (ES-split). The terms of this have been outlined in Table 2,

Parameter	Description	Unit
ρ_{power}	Electrical Component power density. Constant value for each component From literature	kW/kg
ρ_{energy}	Electrical component energy density. Constant value for each component From literature	WH/kg
λ	Electrical component failure rate. Constant value for each component From Literature	Failures per Flight Hour
η	Electrical component efficiency. Constant value From Literature	%
X_{EPU}	EPU quantity (2x4,.....2x1)	QTY
Power(t)	EPU shaft power requirements in kW over mission profile	kW, s
Altitude(t)	EPU shaft power requirements in kW over mission profile	m, s
H-factor	Hybridisation factor for power split between turboshaft and EPUs	%
ES-split	Electrical source split supplying EPU from generators and battery (below 900m)	%

and Table 4.

Figure 9: Hybridisation and energy source sweep process within SST.

The generated outputs from the H-factor and ES split sweep are total system weight, weight breakdown, efficiency and input shaft power demand required by the generator. These are based on amalgamation of peak power instances throughout the flight mission and failure cases in order to size the system for the different power flows associated. A solution is generated for each H-factor and ES split combination.

The output data is generated in the form lookup tables and act as the main interface to the wider power train design and modelling of the consortium. The estimation of weight enables the use of the SST for sensitivity analysis of the electrical network weight against H-Factor and ES-split informing on the weight contribution to the aircraft and global optimisation of the aircraft design (maximum

take-off weight (MTOW), range and payload of the aircraft are kept constant for the project scope). The power demand based on EPS power flow and efficiency is also used to inform the design of the engine sizing.

An initial failure rate analysis of the baseline EPS architecture (Figure 4) indicated that the most significant failures for the EPS are:

1. Dual generator failure (most critical)
 - Potentially also caused by OEI case in addition to generator failure/s
2. Dual battery failure
3. Dual EPU failure

Approaches to mitigate the impact dual generator or dual battery failures condition were identified as:

1. Adapt hybridisation factor, H , to increase proportion of propulsive power from the turbo-prop.
2. Oversize generators to provide additional power, mitigating loss of 2 other generators.
3. Oversize batteries to mitigate loss of two generators.

The approach to mitigate the impact of dual EPU failure is to increase power output from the remaining EPUs. It should be noted, the studies consider full power compensation with any dual failures, as part of the initial analysis. Work to refine power levels to align with expected emergency thrust requirements is underway.

4.4 Example Results for Variation of Hybridisation Factor and Electrical Power Split

For the first suite of studies, the system was sized to ensure that the aircraft could perform a go-around in the event of a missed approach. The EPUs are all over-sized to mitigate the loss of 2 EPUs. In all cases, for this initial stage, the assumption was made that the battery only supplies power below the 900 m threshold. This was chosen as an example for an initial trade study. The role of the battery in the EPS, and whether it supplies electrical power above 900 m is an area for further investigation within the INDIGO project. Further detail on these specific trade studies and results are presented in [Fong2024].

Error! Reference source not found. shows a sweep of EPS weight between these limits for electrical power split below 900 m and hybridization using the example power profile of Figure 7. By inspection of **Error! Reference source not found.**, the EPS weight is less sensitive to the power split between

generator and battery below 900m, than the level of hybridization between the electrical and non-electrical propulsion systems. This is due to the fact that the generator must be sized for maximum power (which occurs above 900m), regardless of power split with the battery below 900m.

Figure 10: Comparison of total weight of EPS with different levels of hybridization, H, power split between battery and generator below 900 m, and approaches to mitigate loss of a gas turbine and two EPUs, and with no oversizing to accommodate loss of EPUs.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 11: Variation of total weight with H, and variation of power split between generator and battery below 900 m, for oversizing turbo-prop (a), oversizing generators (b) and oversizing battery (c).

Figure 12: Comparison of weight breakdown (by percentage) for the case of 90% electrical power from battery below 900m for mitigation by oversizing turbo-props (a), oversizing batteries (b) and oversizing generators (c).

Figure 13: Comparison of weight breakdown (by percentage) for the case of 10% electrical power from generator below 900m for mitigation by oversizing turbo-prop (a), oversizing batteries (b) and oversizing generator (c).

4.5 Transient modelling

4.5.1 Aims of the Transient Modelling

The aim of the transient modelling was to demonstrate the functional capability of the electrical power system, in response to system failures.

4.5.2 Overview of Transient Models

Figure 14: Representation of the architecture of the aircraft power network employed for transient emulation.

Figure 14 illustrates the architecture of one half of the aircraft power network employed for transient emulation. It features a one engine and four electrical-propeller (e-propeller) aircraft topology with two permanent magnet synchronous machines (PMSMs) operating as generators, and four PMSMs functioning as motors to drive propellers. This architecture will be replicated on the other wing of the aircraft, with interconnection possible between the two sides. At this initial stage, only one half of the architecture has been modelled. The gas turbine will also drive a turbo prop (not modelled here as it is not directly part of the EPS). It is important to note that this network can be extended to a two-engine and eight e-propeller system, and energy storage systems (batteries) will be further incorporated into this network in the next phase of this project.

The DC distribution system connects generators to the e-propulsion units via voltage source converters (VSCs) operating as active rectifiers (VSC-Gx) and inverters (VSC-Mx). This network serves as the base model to emulate the failure cases described in Table 5 and demonstrate their associated transient

behaviours. The failure cases, outlined in Table 5, include combinations of single and simultaneous failure of more than one motor, and failure of motors and generators with and without a motor or generator already failed.

Table 5: Failure cases for transient emulation.

Failure Cases	Event at t=0.4s	Event at t=0.8s	Event at t=1.2s
Case 1	Motor speed change (0.5pu to 1.0pu)	M1 fails to operate	M4 fails to operate
Case 2	Motor speed change (0.5pu to 1.0pu)	M1 & M4 fail to operate	--
Case 3	Motor speed change (0.5pu to 1.0pu)	M1 fails to operate	G1 fails to operate
Case 4	Motor speed change (0.5pu to 1.0pu)	M1 & M4 fail to operate	G1 fails to operate
Case 5	Motor speed change (0.5pu to 1.0pu)	G1 fails to operate	M1 fails to operate
Case 6	Motor speed change (0.5pu to 1.0pu)	G1 fails to operate	M1 & M4 fail to operate

Figure 15: A block diagram of the MATLAB/Simulink based aircraft power simulation model.

The electrical power system in Figure 14, was modelled in MATLAB/Simulink, as shown in Figure 15. It includes generation systems composed of two equivalent generator submodules, a DC distribution system featuring equivalent DC network impedance and circuit breakers, and propulsion systems consisting of four VSC-interfaced PMSM motors. Work to integrate the energy storage system (batteries) is on-going. The components, configuration, control systems, and parameters of these submodules are described in the subsections below.

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

4.5.1.1 Generation system

Figure 16: Block diagram of the MATLAB/Simulink based generation system.

Figure 17: A block diagram of the generation system active rectifier DC link voltage control unit.

Figure 16 illustrates the generation system of the Simulink model. The PMSM functioning as a generator typically operates with constant speed regulation via mechanical system control. Since this section focuses on the electrical transient modelling and simulation, this submodule has been modelled as a constant frequency grid from an electrical perspective. The key parameters of this PMSM equivalent are presented in Table 6. The PMSM equivalent, modelled as a constant frequency grid, is interfaced with the DC distribution system through a three-level active rectifier VSC. The switching frequency and DC link capacitor parameters for this active rectifier are provided in in Table 6.

The block diagram of the droop control and inner current and outer voltage nested control for a PMSM active rectifier DC link voltage is depicted in Figure 17. The droop control mechanism enables the two-generation system to share the load proportionally according to their capacities. In this model, the two-

generation systems share the load evenly with a droop coefficient of 1%. The PMSM interfaced active rectifier establishes a controllable DC voltage in the DC network by employing an inner current and outer voltage nested control scheme. The output of the droop control serves as the command for the outer DC-link voltage controller. The PI control parameters of this controller are tuned according to the symmetrical optimum criterion, as detailed in [Leonhard 2012, Blasko 1997], and are listed in Table 6.

The q-axis current resulting from the DC-link voltage controller, along with the zero d-axis current, acts as the current reference for the inner current controller. The PI control parameters for the inner current controller are tuned according to the technical optimum criterion, as specified in [Leonhard 2012, Blasko 1997], and are given in Table 6. A phase-locked loop (PLL) is used to detect the frequency and phase of the PMSM generator's constant frequency grid, which is then used for abc-dq-abc transformation. Space vector modulation (SVM) is employed to generate the pulse signals that drive the switches of the active rectifier. These pulses are synthesized by injecting a zero-sequence signal into the sinusoidal reference signals produced by the inner current control loop and dq-abc transformation.

Table 6: MATLAB/Simulink based aircraft power simulation model parameters.

Submodules & System Components	Symbol	Unit	Value
DC Link Nominal Voltage	Vn_{DC}	kV	3
DC Link Nominal Current	In_{DC}	kA	0.333
DC Link Capacitance	C_{DC}	F	0.0382
DC Distribution Equivalent Resistance	R_{DC}	Ω	
DC Distribution Equivalent Inductance	L_{DC}	H	
Generation side			
PMSM Nominal Power	Sn_{PMSM-G}	kVA	1000
PMSM Nominal Voltage (Phase to Ground, RMS)	Vn_{PMSM-G}	kV	1.844
PMSM Nominal Current	In_{PMSM-G}	kA	0.313
PMSM Nominal Frequency	f_{PMSM-G}	Hz	50
PMSM Pole Pairs	pp_{PMSM-G}	--	2
PMSM Stator d-axis Inductance	$L_{dPMSM-G}$	H	0.00938
PMSM Stator q-axis Inductance	$L_{qPMSM-G}$	H	0.00938
PMSM Stator Resistance Per Phase	R_{PMSM-G}	Ω	0.02947
VSC (Active Rectifier) Switching Frequency	f_{SW-G}	kHz	20
Motor side			

PMSM Nominal Power	$S_{n_{PMSM-M}}$	kVA	200
PMSM Nominal Voltage (Phase to Ground, RMS)	$V_{n_{PMSM-M}}$	kV	1.844
PMSM Nominal Current	$I_{n_{PMSM-M}}$	kA	0.0625
PMSM Nominal Frequency	f_{PMSM-M}	Hz	50
PMSM Pole Pairs	pp_{PMSM-M}	--	2
PMSM Stator d-axis Inductance	$L_{d_{PMSM-M}}$	H	0.0168
PMSM Stator q-axis Inductance	$L_{q_{PMSM-M}}$	H	0.0168
PMSM Stator Resistance Per Phase	R_{PMSM-M}	Ω	0.2947
PMSM Inertia Constant	H_{PMSM}	--	0.01
PMSM Rotor Inertia	J_{PMSM}	$Kg \cdot m^2$	0.16211
VSC (Inverter) Switching Frequency	f_{SW-M}	kHz	20

4.5.1.2 Propulsion system

Figure 18: Block diagram of the MATLAB/Simulink based propulsion system.

Figure 18 illustrates the interface between the electrically driven propeller and associated electrical motor in the Simulink model. The PMSM, functioning as a motor driving the propeller, is interfaced with the DC distribution network through a DC/AC inverter at its electrical ports. The switching frequency and filter parameters for this DC/AC inverter are provided in in Table 7. Furthermore, the propeller is modelled using a controllable torque source that represents an ideal source of mechanical energy. This mechanical source equivalent is connected to the mechanical rotational conserving port of the PMSM rotor, with rotor speed and phase sensed by mechanical sensors.

Figure 19: A block diagram of the generation system PMSM speed control unit.

The PMSM-interfaced DC/AC converter regulates rotor speed using a field-oriented control structure, which includes an inner current loop and an outer speed loop. As shown in Figure 19, the speed reference along with the measured speed from mechanical sensors are given as the input for the speed controller. The PI control parameters of this controller are tuned according to the symmetrical optimum criterion, as detailed in [Leonhard 2012, Blasko 1997], and are listed in Table 7. The speed controller outputs the electromagnetic torque reference that determines the q-axis current reference. This q-axis current reference and the zero d-axis current reference act as the current commands for the inner current controller. The PI control parameters for the inner current controller are tuned according to the technical optimum criterion, as specified in [Leonhard 2012, Blasko 1997], and are given in Table 7. In addition, SVM is further employed to generate the pulse signals that drive the switches of the inverter. These pulses are synthesized by injecting a zero-sequence signal into the sinusoidal reference signals produced by the inner current control loop and dq-abc transformation.

Table 7: MATLAB/Simulink based aircraft power simulation model control parameters.

Submodules & System Components	Symbol	Value
DC Voltage Controller PI Proportional Gain	kp_{DC-G}	0.0063
DC Voltage Controller PI Integral Gain	ki_{DC-G}	0.0041
Current Controller PI Proportional Gain	kpi_G	12.506
Current Controller PI Integral Gain	kii_G	0.0318
Speed Controller PI Proportional Gain	kp_w	15.5628
Speed Controller PI Integral Gain	ki_w	0.0017
Current Controller PI Proportional Gain	kpi_M	56.278
Current Controller PI Integral Gain	kii_M	0.0573

4.5.1.3 Transient Emulation

This section presents the simulation results from the transient emulation of failure scenarios outlined in Table 5 applied to the Simulink models described in Section 4.5.2.2.

As shown Figure 20-Figure 25, for all the failure cases, initially, all the PMSM motors drive the propeller at half-rated speed until the first event is triggered at $t=0.4s$. At 0.4s, all the PMSM motors accelerate to their rated speed. Taking Figure 20 as an example, upon the activation of this event (shown in Figure 20(a)), it can be observed from Figure 20(b) that all the PMSM motor power presents an overshoot and then settles at a steady-state value that is double the motor power operating at half-rated speed. The same behaviour is observed in the PMSM generator power, with both PMSM generators sharing the load power equally due to the implementation of droop control (Figure 20(e)). Due to the increase in speed and power, the DC output voltage at the generator-side active rectifier and the DC network increases and reaches a steady state after minimal oscillations, as shown in Figure 20(d) and 20(g). Correspondingly, the DC current of both the generation and propulsion systems and the AC current of the generation equivalent constant frequency grid settle at double the current value at steady state after oscillations, as depicted in Figure 20(c) and Figure 20(f) and Figure 20(h) and (i), respectively.

Failure Case 1: Cascaded Single Motor Failure

This motor failure scenario involves a PMSM motor (M1) failure followed by another PMSM motor (M4) failure at different stages of the case study. Upon the failure of M1, as illustrated in Figure 20(b-i), its active power and reactive power reach to zero after exhibiting a short-period transient oscillation in response to the failure case while the rest of motors maintain stable operation. The DC current of the inverter interfaced with M1 exhibits remarkable variation before eventually stabilizing at zero, as depicted in Figure 20(c-i). Owing to the failure of M1 and the resulting power drop in the propulsion system, it is obvious from Figure 20(d)- Figure 20(i) that the generation system active rectifier output voltage, the active power, the DC current, and the generator equivalent grid AC current of both generation systems decrease to 75% of their steady-state value before the activation of M1 failure, following a short-period transient oscillation. The simulated system exhibits similar transient behaviours in response to the failure of M4.

Figure 20: Simulation results of the failure case 1 as described in Table 5.

Failure Case 2: Dual (simultaneous) Motor Failure

This case study simulates a scenario of simultaneous dual motor failure, specifically involving two PMSM motors, M1 and M4. Following the simultaneous failure of M1 and M4, as illustrated in Figure 21(b), the active power and reactive power of M1 and M4 decay to zero after exhibiting a short-period transient oscillation. Meanwhile, the remaining two motors continue to maintain stale operation. The DC current of the inverters interfaced with M1 and M4 stabilizes at zero after a brief period of oscillation, while the other two inverters remain constant, as depicted in Figure 21(c-i). By comparing Figure 21(b) and (c) with Figure 20(b) and (c), it can be observed that the transient and steady-state behaviour of the system's response for each PMSM motor and its interfacing inverter is consistent between the cascade single motor failure scenario and the dual simultaneous motor failure scenario. This similarity is

attributed to the independent speed control mechanism implemented to each PMSM motor system.

Figure 21: Simulation results of the failure case 2.

In the dual simultaneous motor failure scenario, a comparison of the simulation results shown in Figure 21(d) to 21(i) with those in Figure 20(d) to 20(i) reveals that the generator-side system exhibits a consistent steady-state response, similar to that observed in the cascade single motor failure scenario. However, in terms of transient behaviour following the activation of motor failures, the dual simultaneous motor failure scenario shows a generation system response with a higher overshoot, more pronounced oscillations, and a longer settling time to reach steady state than the cascade single motor failure scenario. Using the generating system's active rectifier DC current as an example, as shown in Figure 20(f-i) and Figure 21(f-i), the maximum overshoot of the DC current under the single motor failure scenario is 81.41A, while under the dual motor failure scenario, it increases to 102.77A.

Failure Case 3: Single motor failure and subsequent generator failure.

Figure 22: Simulation results of the failure case 3.

This case is utilised to investigate the system response to the failure of a single PMSM motor followed by a subsequent generator failure. Upon the activation of M1 failure at $t=1.2s$, the system exhibits behaviours similar to those observed in Failure Case 1. In addition, after the generator failure is activated at $t=1.6s$, the propulsion system remains stable with negligible transient behaviours, as illustrated in Figure 22(a) to (c). Following the failure of generator G1, as shown in Figure 22(e-i), (f-i), and (h), the output power of G1, the DC current of its interfacing active rectifier, and the equivalent AC grid current from G1 all decrease to zero. As a consequence of the zero output power of G1, the droop control loop for G1 can no longer regulate the DC voltage reference of G1 active rectifier and its output voltage maintain at the rated value as in Figure 22(d-i). With G1 out of operation, G2 takes over and supplies all the power consumed by the propulsion system. Consequently, the output power of G2, the DC

current of its interfacing active rectifier, and the equivalent AC grid current all double at steady state, as shown in Figure 22(e-ii), Figure 22(f-ii), and Figure 22(i). In addition, as illustrated in Figure 22(d-ii), the DC output voltage of G2 interfacing active rectifier increases following the failure of G1, due to the rise of G2 output power.

Failure Case 4: Dual motor failure and subsequent generator failure.

Figure 23: Simulation results of the failure case 4.

This case study presents the system response to the simultaneous failure of double PMSM motors, followed by a subsequent generator failure. When M1 and M4 fail simultaneously at $t=1.2s$, the system exhibits behaviours similar to those observed in Failure Case 2. In addition, after the generator failure is activated at $t=1.6s$, the propulsion system remains stable with negligible transient behaviours, as illustrated in Figure 23(a) to (c). Following the failure of generator G1, as shown in Figure 23(e-i), (f-i), and (h), the output power of

G1, the DC current of its interfacing active rectifier, and the equivalent AC grid current from exhibit similar behaviour to those in Failure Case 3, but with lower peak response values. In terms of the response of G2, the output power of G2, the DC current of its interfacing active rectifier, the equivalent AC grid current, and the DC output voltage of G2 interfacing active rectifier exhibit similar behaviour to that in Failure Case 3 but with less overshoot with respect to their steady state value.

Failure Case 5: Generator failure and subsequent single motor failure.

Figure 24: Simulation results of the failure case 5.

This failure case is compared with Failure Case 3 to highlight the differences in the system transient response under varying sequences of generation and propulsion system failures. Upon the activation of the generator and motor failures at different stages, the system exhibits similar transient behaviours as observed in Failure Case 3 and ultimately reaches the same steady state as in

that case. By comparing Figure 24(d-ii) with Figure 22(d-ii), it can be observed that the peak response of G2 active rectifier DC voltage before reaching steady state is higher in this case (3015.1V) than in Failure Case 3 (3008.4V). This phenomenon arises from the difference in G2 active power before the activation of the final failure, which is 0.148 MW in Case 3 and 0.396 MW in this case. Correspondingly, as illustrated in Figure 24(e-ii) with Figure 22(e-ii), the maximum power peak response after $t=1.2s$ is 0.334 MW in Case 3 and 0.482 MW in this case, respectively. Comparing Figure 24(f-ii) and 24(i) with Figure 22(f-ii) and 22(i), the peak response of G2 active rectifier DC current (168.50 A) and equivalent grid current (213.04 A) in this case is significantly higher than the values in Case 3 (98.46 A and 141.76 A, respectively). These comparisons reveal that the sequence of generator and propulsion system failures leads to different transient behaviours, particularly in the maximum peak responses of current and voltage.

Failure Case 6: Generator failure and subsequent dual motor failure.

This case is further extended from Failure Case 5 with dual simultaneous PMSM failure. Comparing the simulation results presented in Figure 25 with those of Failure Case 4 and Failure Case 5, it is evident that the peak responses of G2 active rectifier DC voltage before reaching steady state, as well as the DC current and equivalent grid current, are significantly greater than those observed in Failure Case 4 and Failure Case 5.

4.5.3 Implications from Transient Results for EPS Design

The depiction of transient behaviours and the direct comparison of transient responses across different failure cases reveal that the sequence of generator and propulsion system failures, along with the power levels of the failure subsystems, lead to varying transient behaviours. These differences, especially in the maximum peak responses of current and voltage, are crucial factors to be considered for the design and operation of aircraft electrical power systems.

The transient modelling and the developed simulation model enable the accurate sizing and design of components such as capacitors, circuit breakers, and protective relays based on the system's transient response and levels. It ensures that these system components can handle transients without failure, thereby avoiding costly overdesign or risky under-design. Moreover, the transient modelling and simulation work offer a safe and cost-effective way to test and validate system performance under various conditions, ensuring reliability, stability, and efficiency of the aircraft electrical power systems. Future work includes extending the existing network to a 2-engine, 8-propeller electrical system with energy storage system incorporated.

Figure 25: Simulation results of the failure case 6.

5 Outlook and impact on further project tasks

Combustion Chamber Model:

Two first simplified reduced-order models have been developed for a combustion chamber based on the Rich-Burn, Quick-Mix, Lean-Burn (RQL) concept. The first approach uses chemical equilibrium (CE) modelling of the combustion reactions, while the second approach uses a chemical reactor network (CRN).

The combustion chamber model with the CRN approach shows a satisfying agreement with the ICAO engine reference data for the emissions of NO_x , CO and UHC. For this reason, this model is being further developed by adding additional reactors to achieve a higher resolution of the combustion processes. For this purpose, a high-fidelity simulation CFD model of the combustion chamber is currently being under development, which will provide calibration data.

The first simplified reduced-order models are already integrated into the gas turbine model of the hybrid-electric propulsion system via lookup tables based on a plug-and-play principle. This approach allows for a fast integration of further reduced-order combustion chamber models, as planned in Task 2.4.

Propeller Noise Model:

A workflow for the prediction of noise generated by distributed propeller settings with individual power settings has been successfully established and cross-compared with different propeller noise prediction methods highlighting the capability to properly predict noise emissions.

In the framework of deliverable D2.2 it is agreed to apply the workflow for the assessment of different power train designs to support its design with some dedicated noise estimates and such enables a holistic performance assessment of the novel out-of-the-box aircraft layouts studied within INDIGO. The chosen simulation approach is maximally suitable at the specific design stage targeted in WP2 in terms of physical level of approximation and simulation time.

In the framework of WP3 some further joint effort of UoB and DLR is undertaken to also establish prediction methods of higher numerical fidelity and larger computational complexity that are applicable for a final design assessment. Specifically, Actuator Disk (AD) RANS CFD simulations will be provided by project partners to the DLR acoustics branch to enable further evaluation of the expected installation noise effects with the PIANO-IBM approach. For an in-depth validation and improved parameters adjustment of this approach, a generic wind tunnel setup with available experimental data from UoB will be used in conjunction with scale resolving Lattice Boltzmann Simulations. The simulation activity will also provide some high-fidelity results for a posterior cross-validation of the present isolated rotor predictions.

Hybrid Electric Propulsion Model:

The development of the EPS and associated modelling has been presented. The use of EPS development methodology [Jones2021], Strathclyde Systems Tool and electrical transient model has a baseline architecture and preliminary sizing and power flow results including under different hybridisation levels and electrical energy splits.

The next step is to perform more refined studies (updated mission profile and EPU failure power requirements) and inter model integration using the subsequent generated datasets. Inclusion of the battery in the transient model will enable full exploration of the role of the battery during failure modes, and validation of the baseline EPS architecture with respect to system response and stability during failure modes.

6 References

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